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Age And Socio-economic Differences In Widowhood Stress Level In Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined age and socio-economic differences in stress level among widows in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study adopted the ex-post facto design, with a population of 620 widows in all the eight Local Government Areas in Bayelsa State. A sample of 310 widows were selected using the purposive sampling technique; and two research questions and two hypotheses were generated for the study. A researcher-designed instrument tagged 'Widowhood Stress Level Questionnaire' was used to collect data for the study. A reliability index of 0.82 was achieved using the Cronbach alpha method. The data were analyzed using mean for the research questions and independent t-test and one-way ANOVA for the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that widowhood stress was higher and more predominant among old widows than the young widows, and was also higher in widows of the low socio-economic level than those of the medium and high socio-economic levels. Based on the findings, recommendations were made.

Keywords: Age, socio-economic level, differences, stress level, widows

INTRODUCTION

The loss of a spouse is one of the most negative life events that causes much distress to the widow, psychologically, socially, emotionally and spiritually. A widow is a woman who has lost her spouse by death and has not remarried; the state of having lost one's spouse to death is termed 'widowhood' (Iruloh & Williams, 2018). Unfortunately, sickness, diseases and accidents which end up in fatality have turned many women to widows overnight. This fatality brings a sudden and dramatic change in the life of the estranged wife of the deceased and confers on her the status of widowhood. These changes make the wife to be lonely and socially isolated (Fakoya, McCorry, & Donnelly, 2020). Furthermore, the demise of a husband automatically forces the widow to assume certain roles which she never anticipated; taking on most of the physical and psychosocial responsibilities of the late husband such as bearing the financial burden of the family (where there are children), performing the fatherly parental role of discipline, the responsibility of serving as a bridge between her children and her in-laws, and performing chores which

the husband would otherwise perform. These and many other events that occur as a result of the demise of a husband exert tremendous stress on the widow and compel her to cope in one way or the other.

In Nigeria, and indeed Bayelsa State, the death of a husband seems to be more traumatic than the death of a wife due to the double standards and gender roles inherent in customs and traditions. Many women face poverty and diverse forms of violence that culminate in untold hardship following the demise of their husbands due to unjust cultural practices concomitant with stigmatization. For instance, personal observation shows that following the demise of a husband, the grieving widow is deprived of most of her deceased husband's property, forced to shave her hair as a symbol of respect for the corpse, forced to marry one of the brothers of the deceased husband, forced to take an oath of innocence, just to mention but a few of the harsh treatment. These occurrences are also experienced by many widows in various parts of Africa. The UN Division for the Advancement of Women (cited in Muthangya, Kaaria & Katiba, 2018) lamented that the African widows, irrespective of ethnic groups, are among the most vulnerable and destitute women in the region. It further stated that the low status, poverty and violence experienced by widows, stem from various aspects, including discrimination in inheritance custom, the patriarchal nature of society, and the domination of oppressive traditional practices and customary codes, which take precedence over constitutional guarantees of equality, modern laws and international women's human rights standards. These are enough to bring about stress that is capable of causing behavioural breakdown in the life of the widow.

Bereavement through the loss of a spouse is a life event that may be too stress-inducing to the surviving spouse to effectively cope and deal with the loss and adapt to the new situation.

Bereavement due to the death of a husband constitutes a major health hazard to the health of the widowed wife as it crunches her emotional functioning (Hodgkinson, 2014). This inability to bounce back is often manifested in behavioural dysfunctions such as auditory hallucinations, paranoia, self-pity, isolation, aggression, dependency, obsession, regrets, post-traumatic stress behaviours (such as difficulty in being intimate with a member of the opposite sex) and low self-esteem, among others (Barros-Lane, Yang, Vollmann, Allen, Gilmore, & Ellis, 2024). In the same vein, bereavement impacts on the subjective well-being of the bereaved so intensely that it could be viewed as a risk factor for the development of major psychiatric illnesses, particularly if the loss is abrupt and unforeseen. All these pose a lot of challenges on the incapacitated bereaved. Also, a woman who has children automatically becomes a single parent at the demise of her husband. As a single parent, the widow has to face stressors such as demands at home or work place, uncertainty about the future, lack of control over some situations brooding over the past and worrying about the future (Fakoya, McCorry & Donnelly, 2020).

The foregoing implies that widows inevitably experience varying forms of stress which constitute stressors in their lives. For instance, lack of appropriate social support from significant others (such as friends and relatives) incites feelings of isolation and regrets in the bereaved. If the widow is young, she may perceive the society as cruel and resort to acts that veer from the norms of conduct. An older widow may even contemplate suicide due to feelings of despair (National Council on Aging, 2025). This leaves one to wonder the level of stress that widows experience and ways in which they cope with the inevitability of such stress. In another study, it was reported that young widows go through the roughest times economically, much more than old widows, and concluded that both younger and older widows suffer the same social effect of widowhood, Atindanbila, Bamford, Adatarara, Nuako and Benneth, cited in (Akiyi, 2023).

Scott (2024) describe stress as any type of change that causes physical, emotional or mental strain; the body's response to anything requiring attention or action. Taylor (2016) defined stress as a negative emotional experience accompanied by predictable biochemical, physiological, cognitive and behavioural changes directed towards altering the stressful event or accommodating its effects. Lazarus and Folkman (cited in Baltus, 2015) in their transactional model defined stress as "any circumstance that threatens or is perceived to threaten one's well-being and thereby tax one's coping abilities". More so, Nevid and Rathus (2016) agreed that stress is the mind and body's reaction to the changes in our environment towards 'fight or flight' response activated by hormones which stimulate a variety of physiological changes such as

increased heart rate and blood pressure, faster breathing and muscle tenseness, dilated pupils, increased blood sugar, and dry mouth. Thus, stress is the physiological response of an individual to a stressor. Psychological stress describes what people feel when they are under mental, physical, or emotional pressure; people who experience high levels of psychological stress or who experience it repeatedly over a long period of time may develop health problems (mental and/or physical). Social stress is stress that stems from one's relationships with others and from the social environment in general (Hodgkinson, Beers, Southammakosane, & Lewin, 2014). Therefore, in this study, the researchers consider stress level to be the amount of stress experienced by widows measured by self-report.

What is apparent from the above distinction is that stress is not necessarily internally induced, but rather a phenomenon that is conceptualized as a process of interaction between the individual and his or her environment. Hence, an individual tends to be in an anticipatory situation if he or she feels physically or psychologically threatened. If the initial evaluation of the event shows that it is stressful (primary cognitive appraisal), then the individual evaluates the available coping resources and options at his or her disposal in order to deal with such a stressful situation (secondary cognitive appraisal).

In view of the foregoing, the present study examined age and socioeconomic differences in stress level experienced by widows in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Widows are besieged by a myriad of challenges that adversely affect their psychological, social, economic and spiritual worlds. Most widows never bounce back to normal life after the mourning period as they manifest diverse symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder such as social withdrawal, panic attacks, alcoholism and other behaviours that interfere with their work, personal and social life. Unfortunately, no emotional preparation was made as to the shock of the sudden death of a spouse, and this makes it traumatizing especially for an unprepared widow to rear her children alone. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, no research on widowhood stress has been carried out in Bayelsa State, and this vacuum created necessitated the formulation of this study. Therefore, the problem of this study is to investigate age and socio-economic differentials in widowhood stress level in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate age and socio-economic differentials in widowhood stress level in Bayelsa State of Nigeria. Specifically, the study has the following objectives, to:

1. examine the influence of age of widows on their stress level in Bayelsa State.
2. determine the influence of socio-economic status of widows on their stress level in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. Is there any influence of age of widows on their stress level in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the influence of socio-economic status of widows on their stress level in Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to further guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of stress level between old and young widows in Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of stress level among widows with high, medium and low socio-economic status in Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for this study was the ex-post facto or causal comparative research design. Kpolovie (2010) described ex-post facto design as "a design which involves the methodological approach for eliciting possible or probable antecedents of events that have already occurred and which cannot be subjected to rigorous manipulation and control by the researcher. The author also opined that ex-post-facto design studies retrospectively the effects and consequences of events that have already occurred in an uncontrolled manner. The researchers deemed the above design suitable for the present study because data collected from the widows were analyzed the way they were without manipulating any variable.

The population of the study was made up of 620 widows from all the eight Local Government Areas in Bayelsa State. This was made up of 59, 72, 92, 60, 103, 53, 66 and 115 respectively for Brass, Ekeremor, Kolokuma/Opokuma, Nembe, Ogbia, Sagbama, Southern Ijaw and Yenagoa Local Government Areas respectively (Bayelsa State Ministry of Women Affairs, 2019).

A sample size of 310 widows of the total population was selected through the purposive sampling technique for the study. This comprised 92, 103 and 115 widows from Kolokuma/Opokuma, Ogbia and Yenagoa Local Government Areas respectively. Only women known to be widows in their communities, work places, religious worship centres and social clubs in these Local Government Areas were used for the study. The justification for selecting widows from these three Local Government Areas was because they had a large concentration of widows, and their number made up (50%) of widows in the area. The instrument for the study, named Widowhood Stress Level Questionnaire (WSLQ) was developed by the researchers. The WSLQ instrument has two separate segments, namely A and B. Segment A sought information on demographic data of the respondents, and Segment B sought information on widowhood stress level. The response pattern consisted of a four-point rating scale of the following options: Very High Level (VHL)- 4 points; High Level (HL) -3 points; Low Level (VL)- 2points, and Very Low Level - (VLL) 1-point

The face and content validity of the instrument was estimated by giving copies of the instrument to two experts, one in Guidance and Counselling, and the other in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The experts carefully scrutinized the instrument for suitability, comprehensiveness and clarity of the items, by modifying the items that were ambiguous in line with the study. Furthermore, the expert from Measurement and Evaluation validated the instrument on the basis of the construct dimension part of the instrument. All the corrections, comments, and contributions on the instrument by the validation process were constructively and judiciously integrated into the final draft of the instrument. Arising from the authentication of the instrument for validity by the two experts, out of the original 41 items drafted, a total of 36 items were finally approved for this study.

The reliability of the “Widowhood Stress Level Questionnaire (WSLQ) was administered to 30 widows from Sagbama Local Government Area in Bayelsa State that were not part of the main population of the study. The administration of the instrument was carried out once and the scores obtained from the administration of the instrument were utilized to compute the internal consistency of the instrument reliability coefficient values of all variables within the instrument, utilizing Cronbach Alpha analysis strategy. The internal consistency reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.73. This coefficient value was considered to be high enough to sustain the applicability of the instrument for data collection in the study.

The researchers directly administered copies of the instrument to the respondents, with the help of two trained research assistants. The researcher presented a letter of introduction explaining the purpose and nature of the study to heads of worship centres, community chiefs and the respondents, and assuring the respondents that it is mainly for educational purpose, stressing the need for their honest and sincere responses while assuring them of confidentiality of the information that will be collected. The researcher also explained to the respondents how to fill the questionnaire forms. After copies of the instrument were duly responded to, the researcher and the assistants retrieved the questionnaire forms from the respondents. Data collected in the study were analyzed with both descriptive and inferential statistical tools.

The simple percentage was used to answer the demographic data of the respondents, mean was utilized to answer the research questions and t-test analysis, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and scheffe’s multiple comparison test (post hoc analysis) were used to test all the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In addition, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used for the analysis.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *Is there any influence of age of widows on their stress level in Bayelsa State?*

Table 1: Summary of mean scores of the stress level between young and old widows

S/N	Stress level	Mean Scores			Decision
		Young	Old	Total	
1	Being a widow makes me feel ashamed	2.57	3.02	2.84	Accepted
2	It has been difficult for me to be in a relationship with the opposite sex	3.12	3.18	3.15	Accepted
3	As a widow, people treat me with contempt	2.78	3.01	2.91	Accepted
4	Since I became a widow, I have been experiencing feelings of inferiority	2.90	3.21	3.08	Accepted
5	As a widow, I can't attend meetings with married women due to my culture	2.56	2.83	2.72	Accepted
6	My late husbands' family has taken everything he had due to customs/traditions.	2.52	2.52	2.52	Accepted
7	As a widow, I am always ill because of disappointments, frustrations and anxiety.	2.30	2.91	2.66	Accepted
8	My sex drive is low since I became a widow and it has affected my menstrual cycle	2.75	2.94	2.86	Accepted
9	My husband's family does not care about me or my children's welfare.	2.75	3.06	2.93	Accepted
10	I have been experiencing financial difficulties due to my husband's death	2.79	3.02	2.93	Accepted
11	My relationship with my in-laws has gone cold since the death of my husband.	2.59	2.84	2.74	Accepted
12	As a widow I often regret marrying my late husband	2.29	2.78	2.58	Accepted
13	Thoughts of my late husband make me feel betrayed.	2.43	2.70	2.59	Accepted
14	The constant reminder of my widowhood status by cultural status makes me sick	2.21	2.73	2.52	Accepted
15	I feel depressed because my close friends no longer associate with me	2,21	2.50	2.38	Rejected
16	Being in a rural area makes it even more difficult for me to access financial support	2.41	2.71	2.61	Accepted
	Grand Mean	2.58	2.87	2.75	Accepted

Cut-off mean = 2.50; Young Widows = 126; Older Widows = 184 and Total = 310

The data represented in Table 1 shows that the mean scores of young widows in all items except items 7, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 were greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. However, the mean scores of old widows in all items were greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that all items except item 15 were accepted. The grand mean score of old widows (2.87) was greater than that of the young widows (2.58), with a total grand mean score of (2.75) being greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This simply means that old widows' mean score on stress level is better than that of the young widows. Consequently, the observed difference in the mean scores was subjected to t-test analysis in order to ascertain if the difference is significant or not (see Table 3).

Research Question Two: *What is the influence of socio-economic status of widows on their stress level in Bayelsa State?*

Table 2: Summary of mean scores of the stress level among widows with high, medium and low SES

S/N	Stress Level	Mean Scores				Decision
		High	Medium	Low	Total	
1	Being a widow makes me feel ashamed	3.00	2.82	2.76	2.84	Accepted
2	It has been difficult for me to be in a relationship with the opposite sex	3.24	3.07	3.19	3.15	Accepted
3	As a widow, people treat me with contempt	3.04	2.97	2.78	2.91	Accepted
4	Since I became a widow, I have been experiencing feelings of inferiority	2.89	3.15	3.13	3.08	Accepted
5	As a widow, I can't attend meetings with married women due to my culture	3.03	2.63	2.61	2.72	Accepted
6	My late husbands' family has taken everything he had due to customs/traditions.	2.75	2.61	2.30	2.52	Accepted
7	As a widow, I am always ill because of disappointments, frustrations and anxiety.	2.82	2.68	2.56	2.66	Accepted
8	My sex drive is low since I became a widow and it has affected my menstrual cycle	3.00	2.81	2.83	2.86	Accepted
9	My husband's family do not care about me or my children's welfare.	2.83	2.98	2.94	2.93	Accepted
10	I have been experiencing financial difficulties due to my husband's death	3.18	2.82	2.88	2.93	Accepted
11	My relationship with my in-laws has gone cold since the death of my husband.	3.01	2.75	2.56	2.74	Accepted
12	As a widow I often regret marrying my late husband	2.40	2.69	2.58	2.58	Accepted
13	Thoughts of my late husband makes me feel betrayed.	2.89	2.41	2.58	2.59	Accepted
14	The constant reminder of my widowhood status by cultural status makes me sick	2.36	2.66	2.49	2.52	Accepted
15	I feel depressed because my close friends no longer associate with me	2.54	2.32	2.35	2.38	Rejected
16	Being in a rural area makes it even more difficult for me to access financial support	2.53	2.75	2.53	2.61	Accepted
	Grand Mean	2.84	2.76	2.69	2.75	Accepted

Cut-off mean = 2.50; High = 72; Medium = 114; Low = 124 and Total = 310

The data represented in Table 2 reveals that the mean scores of widows with high socio-economic status in all items except items 12 and 14 were greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that all items, except items 12 and 14 were accepted by the widows. Alternatively, the mean scores of widows with medium socio-economic status in all items except items 13 and 15 were greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that all items except items 13 and 15 were accepted. On the other hand, the mean scores of widows with low socio-economic status in all items except items 6, 14 and 15 were greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. The grand mean score of widows with high socio-economic status (2.84) was greater than that of the widows with medium socio-economic status (2.76), this in turn was greater than widows with low socio-economic status (2.67) with a total grand mean score of (2.75), being greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This simply means that, widows with high socio-economic status mean score on stress level was better than widows with medium and low socio-economic status. Consequently, the observed difference in the mean scores was subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in order to confirm if the difference was significant or not (See Table 4).

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of stress level between old and young widows in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: t-test analysis of the difference in the mean scores of stress level between young and old widows

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Sig	Decision at P < 0.05
Young Widows	126	2.58	0.41	308	-7.299	1.96	0.000	*
Old Widows	184	2.87	0.30					

* = Significant at 0.05 alpha level; N = 310

The data presented in Table 3 reveals that, the t-test analysis is significant at 0.05 alpha level because the calculated absolute t-test value of -7.299 is greater than the critical table t-test value of 1.960 at 0.05 alpha level with 308 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which states that, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of stress level between young and old widows in Bayelsa State was upheld.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of stress level among widows with high, medium and low socio-economic status in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) difference in the mean scores of stress level among widows with high, middle and low SES

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at P < 0.05
Between groups	1.052	2	0.526	3.732	0.025	*
Within groups	43.249	307	0.141			
Total	44.300	309				

* = Significant at 0.05 alpha Level; Critical F 2, 307 = 3.02; N = 310.

The data presented in Table 4 shows that the one-way analysis of variance is significant at p < 0.05 alpha level because, the calculated F- value of 3.732 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.02 at 0.05 alpha level with 2 and 307 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of stress level among widows with high, middle and low socio-economic status in Bayelsa State was rejected. The alternative hypothesis which states that, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of stress level among widows with high, middle and low socio-economic status in Bayelsa was upheld. To establish the order of effectiveness of widows' socio-economic status and direction of significance, the mean scores were subjected to Scheffe's multiple comparison tests for a post hoc analysis (See Table 5).

Table 5: Summary of Scheffe's post hoc analysis of stress level among widows based on SES

Socio-economic status	Socio-economic status	Mean Difference	Sig
Low	High	-0.152*	0.205
	Medium	-0.064	0.422
Medium	High	-0.087	0.303
	Low	0.064	0.422
High	Medium	0.087	0.303
	Low	0.152*	0.205

The data presented in Table 5 reveals the Scheffe's post hoc test of stress level among widows based on their socio-economic status. The Table shows that the mean difference between widows in the high and middle socio-economic status is 0.087, between high and low socio- economic status is 0.152 and between middle and low socio- economic status is 0.064. This implies that widows with high socio-economic status were the most effective, followed by those with middle and the least were the widows with low socio- economic status in handling stress level.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In relation to widows' age and stress level, the result in Table 1 shows that a significant difference exists in the mean scores of stress level between young and old widows. From Table 3 it reveals that old widows' mean score on stress level was better than the young widows'. The reason may be connected with their age and the fear they are nursing especially because it may be a bit difficult for them to remarry at that age. Moreover, because they have been in marriage longer, and having more children than the young widows, the stress of taking care of many children may create a lot of uncertainties in them. The literature also supports this finding that differences exist in age responses to stress (Scott, Sliwinski, & Blanchard- Fields, 2013). In their study on age differences in daily stress, Scott et. al. (2013) found that older age was associated with less of a decrease in PA when exposed to stressor. In line with this finding, Williams and Ugwu (2017) in their study using 370 widows examined differences in their adjustment strategies on the basis of age and educational level in Rivers State, Nigeria. The result showed that the widows differed significantly on the basis of age and educational attainment. The finding may probably be as a result of their advancement in age that might limit youthful activity (Falana, 2013). Korieh, (2006) also observed that although the underlying pattern is not entirely clear, it appears that older widows are especially likely to be disturbed when they seek out new sexual partners (perhaps out of boredom/loneliness) or become aware of changes in themselves due to the passage of time. In general, transitions that are entered into voluntarily are considered less distressing than those that happen involuntarily and older widows are more adept to such transitions in comparison to younger ones. On the contrary, a study carried out in Bangladesh found that aged or older widows were found to be unstable due to experiencing challenges within their families because they were excluded from decision making, deprived of respect and access to medical facilities. This implies that they were experiencing some form of stress (Sarker, 2024).

The result in Table 2 reveals that the mean scores of widows with high socio- economic status was greater than those with medium and low socio-economic statuses. The grand mean score of idows with high socio-economic status was greater than that of the widows with medium socio-economic status; this in turn was greater than widows with low socio-economic status. This simply means that, widows with high socio-economic status mean score on stress level was better than widows with medium and low socio-economic status. Consequently, the observed difference in the mean scores were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in order to confirm if the difference was significant or not as seen in Table 4. The result also shows that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of stress level among widows with high, medium and low socio-economic status. Similarly, the scheffe result in Table 5 shows mean difference between widows in the high and medium socio-economic status, between high and low socio-economic status and between medium and low socio- economic status. This implies that widows of the high socio- economic status were the most effective, followed by those with medium and the least were the widows with low socio- economic status in handling stress level. The reason may probably be attributed to them having more financial stability than their counterparts in the medium and low socio-economic statuses. The outcome of this finding might be because widowhood in most cases was associated with poverty probably as a result of the belief that their late husbands were the primary providers of the home. Moreover, in support of this assertion, a study undertaken in India found that majority (85%) of widows faced financial challenges (George & Menon, 2022). Similarly, another study submits that the poor economic condition of widows brought about by loss of financial support from their late husbands was responsible for their being stressed out (De Leo et al, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The study shows that a significant difference exists in the mean scores of stress level between young and old widows. This implies that old widows' mean score on stress level was better than young widows. Therefore, age has significant influence on stress level of widows. Old widows mean score on stress level was better than the young widows'. Also, a significant difference was found to exist in the mean scores of stress level among widows with high, medium and low socio-economic status. The results also reveal that

widows with high socio-economic status mean score on stress level was better than widows with medium and low socio-economic status. This means widows with low socio-economic status experienced more stress than those of medium and high socio-economic status. In other words, socio-economic status has a significant influence on stress level of widows.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Consequent on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Young widow due to their age, should concentrate on learning a trade to alleviate their financial challenges during the period of widowhood. Therefore, counsellors should employ bereavement counselling in assisting the widows,
2. Widows in medium and low socio-economic status should endeavour to think less about their situation in order to reduce the stress level associated with widowhood in the society. The Dialectical Behavioural Psychotherapy founded by Marsha Linehan in the 1970s, should be employed by counsellors to assist the widows in reducing their stress level. The therapy consists of using a combination of cognitive and behavioural therapy centred on four main skills, which includes core mindfulness, distress tolerance, interpersonal effectiveness and emotional regulation

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